

Grant application for Open Life Science second cohort (OLS-2)

Applied to: [EOSC-Life Training Open Call](#)

Application Details

Application Title: *Training Open Science Community Ambassadors with Open Life Science Principles*

Type of support you are applying for

This proposal is for support in the following areas:

- a) *Support for execution of training*
- b) *Activities that support capacity building*

Additional supporting documents (e.g. agenda from previous version of course as document, associated deliverable):

- [Schedule from first edition of the OLS program](#)
- [Details for personnel cost hour calculations for one cohort](#)
- **Letters of support were provided by:**
 - Neil Chue Hong, Director of Software Sustainability Institute
 - Dr Bastian Greshake Tzovaras, co-founder of openSNP
 - Mateusz Kuzak, eScience Center
 - Dr Andrew Stewart, University of Manchester Open Research Working Group Co-Chair
 - Dr Naomi Penfold, Community Manager, eLife
 - Dr Fotis E. Psomopoulos, Co-lead ELIXIR Training Platform
 - Dr Emmy Tsang, Innovation Community Manager, eLife

About the training

Aims and objectives of the course including learning outcomes:

Aim:

Open Life Science trains and mentors early-career researchers and potential academic leaders in open science skills and open project leadership. As scientists, we are provided training and guidance in how to conduct research in the lab, design algorithms, analyse data and publish them. However, we rarely learn about important research skills such as open science principles for tooling and road mapping of projects, planning reproducible workflows with open data, FAIRification of scientific research objects, involving others in our work, and leading an inclusive community.

Modern bioinformatics communities stand in the interface of computational and biological research. This interdisciplinary position requires us to develop collaborative projects by implementing such “open by design” principles in our research projects systematically -- skills that aren’t necessarily taught at university or graduate school level.

The Open Life Science program has been designed to address this gap in research by providing essential training and mentorship to advance open research practices in bioinformatics. We would like to offer the opportunity to EOSC-Life members to join this program by reserving slots specifically for EOSC-Life members who would like to develop their ongoing or a new idea for a project during the program. In addition, we would invite new mentors from the EOSC-Life community and onboard them by providing training in mentorship skills.

Objective:

Over 16 weeks, participants work on their bioinformatics research or related projects with the help of their mentors from the program who are matched based on the specific skill-requirement. They get trained on different best-practices in Open Science over the online cohort calls, which feature collaborative group discussions, networking, and a range of guest speakers and experts sharing their insights from working on open science topics. These topics include methods such as depositing data openly, open hardware, open source software, citizen science, and open training. Additionally they learn open science dissemination methods such as preprints, preregistration, open peer review, open access, and FAIRification of research components. Participants are also introduced to hands-on skills such as collaboration on GitHub, open communication of their work and community building that encourages bringing in new contributors from their local communities and creating inclusive pathways for them to engage with the project in the long term.

Mentors and mentees meet on alternate weeks, creating a rhythm of cohort call one week, and mentor call the other. Mentors also receive training to deliver their mentorship effectively and are supported in their work by the program organisers. Each principle is complemented by assignments that help participants apply the learned skills to their projects with guidance from their mentor in mentor-mentee calls, and other participants during coworking sessions.

Learning outcomes:

By the end of the program, our program participants will:

- receive one-to-one support in their projects from their mentors, who will guide them to develop a clear vision of their projects
- create a roadmap by defining their project development plan and community engagement guidelines
- set up an online repository (if they do not have one already) to start building their project openly and add an appropriate open license to their projects
- gain an understanding of what open research approaches and best practices exist and what tools they can apply in bioinformatics research and community
- potentially launch their projects (if the project is new) and involve other members to promote open practices in bioinformatics community
- graduate from the Open Life Science program by presenting their work, progress, and learnings over the 16 week and sharing plans for the long-term sustainability of their projects

In parallel, the mentors will:

- receive training on mentorship from professional instructors
- exchange ideas and tips with other mentors and organisers
- learn how to guide people through an open project
- learn how to give feedback and provide support to early stage researchers

Describe which training methods you will use and how they will enable the participants to apply the new knowledge/skills?

Training Methods

Open Life Science training uses a combination of classroom-style online training (cohort calls), group discussions (online break-out sessions and coworking sessions) and one-on-one support (mentor-mentee calls). In this process, we use a variety of methods and learning styles to engage with our participants that include:

- short expert talks (10-15 minutes)
- discussion groups
- reflective short-form writing in shared documents
- resources for self-paced learning
- personal assignments
- guided evaluation of their work with their mentors
- coworking sessions with other participants

This blend of training methods has proven to be successful in our previous cohort, as it encourages and facilitates engagement from a range of participants and personalities.

In parallel, mentors receive training from experts, and are invited to participate in discussion groups on mentoring skills and share their experiences with other mentors.

Enabling participants to apply new skills

- Collaborative-documentation during online training and breakout discussions in smaller groups ensures that quieter and shyer participants have as much opportunity to express themselves as louder and more confident voices.
- All the training and learning materials, including recorded videos of the cohort calls, are shared online so that participants can revisit them or catch up if they miss any call.
- Assignments allow them to evaluate their understanding and relevance of the newly introduced topics for their work.
- One-to-one mentoring calls guide mentees to think about how they can apply the newly introduced skills through training and assignments in their projects.
- Self-paced learning materials on open science topics further help them to integrate these ideas into their ongoing work and further discuss them with other participants during the coworking sessions.
- The presentation rehearsal calls before their graduation allow them to put their work from the last 14 weeks into perspective and receive feedback from their peers that they can use for enhancing their work before and after their graduation.
- Mentors gain additional leadership skills in mentoring and giving feedback from professional instructors, and apply them directly with their mentees.

What is the format of the training?

- Remote delivery for training and one-on-one mentorship

Target audience & the training needs (include information how you assess the training needs) expected impacts:

Audience: Open Life Science aims to train early career scientists and researchers primarily in life science and bioinformatics who have a project or project idea related to open science that they would like to develop. This includes postdocs, PhD students, research engineers, PIs, research assistants and individuals working in equivalent roles. Each project is paired with a mentor. Mentors are open science advocates and contributors to one or more Open Science projects or communities. They have hands-on experience with the types of milestones and challenges these projects face. They also benefit from the mentorship experience, formal mentorship training, and networking with the cohort and other mentors.

The first cohort involved 20 project teams (29 individuals) who came from a wide range of backgrounds as data stewards, software engineers, undergraduate students, PhD students, postdocs, PIs, and countries (Brazil, Canada, Germany, India, Japan, Kenya, Netherlands, Nepal, Norway, Russia, Spain, Thailand, UK, and the USA). Among them some were affiliated to EOSC-Life partners (ELIXIR, University of Oxford and University of Manchester). The pool of mentors had a similarly diverse background and geographic spread as the participants. This included mentors and experts from EOSC-Life partners including the University of Manchester,

University of Freiburg, University of Cambridge, EMBL, the ELIXIR training platform and ELIXIR nodes (Germany, Greece, UK, Netherlands).

With this grant, we would expand that by offering up to 10 additional slots for projects from EOSC-Life members and partners via a special call in Q3 of 2020 in collaboration with the leaders of the WP 3, 9, 10 and 11. We are also recruiting mentors for the second cohort, and with the support of this grant we will onboard new members from EOSC-Life partner organisations. We will launch both an open call in Q3 of 2020 and personal invitation to targeted individuals for the mentor selection process and ensure to have a diverse mentor pool with a range of skill sets.

Training needs are assessed via a short application from the interested applicants asking about current project stage, project goals, and willingness to learn open practices. Application form templates can be previewed here: <https://github.com/open-life-science/application-forms>

At the end of the cohort, we expect to see open science projects with clear onboarding and contribution guides that foster strong and inclusive communities, trainees with hands-on online collaborative meeting skills, projects with openly shared and detailed project roadmaps, and a greater awareness of existing open science practices and tools available. We also aim to steer mentors towards stronger mentorship and leadership skills.

Provide the agenda of the last edition of the course if there is any:

Round one of OLS started with an open call for applications for project leads (mentees). The OLS team personally reached out to recruit mentors and experts from their network, based on their interests and expertise in Open Science. We successfully involved over 30 mentors and over 50 experts who showed tremendous support for this project.

Through the open call, we received 28 complete applications, which were evaluated based on rubrics to assess the overall goal of the proposal, the readiness of the applicants to apply Open Science practices in their work and alignment with the aim of the program. 20 projects (29 individuals) were selected to become part of the OLS-1 cohort and matched with a mentor who could provide the guidance they need to develop their projects. These members were based in 5 different continents and worked on their projects in Brazil, Canada, China, Germany, Greece, India, Japan, Kenya, Malaysia, Nepal, Norway, Russia, South Africa, Spain, The Netherlands, UK, and the USA. All the cohort calls were well attended by participants and the recordings were viewed on YouTube multiple times (average 30 views).

18 Projects successfully finished their training with us and graduated in 5 separate calls by sharing developments in their projects with the rest of their cohort members. These graduations were live-streamed on YouTube and each video was viewed over 50 times. All the materials of the program including notes, links to video recording and project details have been archived on our website and are available under a CC-BY license for others to read, reuse, remix and share.

The complete schedule of the last edition can be found in a supporting document and also online at <https://openlifesci.org/ols-1#schedule> with the full syllabus.

Describe any changes you would like to make based on the programme & the feedback of the last iteration and list any feedback you would like to share:

Given the feedback from the last iteration, we would like to provide more opportunities to participants to interact with each other. With the help of this funding, we will expand our capacity to organise and host remote coworking sessions every second week and add two social open agenda or 'quiz' style cohort calls.

Mentors should also receive more support by receiving professional training in mentoring and coaching from an expert training organisation. We will also create more space in the program for mentor-mentor discussions and support.

We intend to extend our open science curriculum with an additional cohort call so that wider topics in Open Science can be discussed in depth during three separate cohort calls (previously two calls). Currently, we cover introductory open science methods in Open Science I (such as hardware, software, data), and open science dissemination in Open Science II (preprints, open access, preregistration, open peer review). Developing a third module for Open Science topics would allow us to cover advanced methods, such as project FAIRification, including publishing data that are FAIR and have a documented provenance. We would love to invite people from EOSC-Life involved in WP1 and WP6 to give expert talks during this call and cover new aspects that we haven't yet covered in our previous cohort.

Finally, we will make our material reusable by EOSC-Life members and generally more FAIR by following the rules described in "Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR" ([Garcia et al. Plos Comp Biol. 2020](#)). To achieve this, all training material will be stored on GitHub repository and properly annotated with schema.org metadata. Collaborative notes will be migrated from Google Docs to GitHub and edited using the collaborative Markdown editor, HackMD (<https://hackmd.io>). All training materials and notes on GitHub will be versioned at the end of the cohort and deposited in Zenodo to link with a DOI. We will also extensively document the program and its structure so EOSC-Life members could implement similar ones in their own community, possibly via the EOSC-Life WP3.

What is the application format:

- Application with selection

Criteria for joining the course - will there be a selection process? If selection process, please add key criteria:

All applications from potential participants are reviewed by at least two potential mentors for each application based on a rubric that help them assess if applicants:

- 1) have a proposal for a project they plan to work on (even if it's only an idea at the initial stages)
- 2) demonstrate intent to learn and apply open methods to their project

Within the scope of this grant, up to 10 additional slots will be dedicated to projects from EOSC-Life members and partners. A special call will be open in the Q3 of 2020 for potential mentee and mentors among EOSC-Life members.

Outline of course content:

The full syllabus and schedule are available online at <https://openlifesci.org/ols-2/schedule/>

Week	Meeting type	Length	Topic	Agenda
Week 01	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	Meet each other and discuss your personal motivation, expectations, working practices and project goals
	Mentors	60 min	Mentor training	
Week 02	Cohort	90 min	Welcome to Open Life Science!	Meet other members of your cohort, Share project vision, Intro to working openly (open canvas)
Week 03	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	Discuss assignments from the cohort call & concrete implementations
	Cohort	90 min	Social Call & Coworking session	
	Mentors	60 min	Mentor training	
Week 04	Cohort	90 min	Tooling and roadmapping for Open projects	Working with GitHub as a community hub: Markdown as a tool to make websites, Licence, Goals and Roadmap, Contributors, Code of Conduct
Week 05	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	
	Cohort	60 min	GitHub Tutorial	

Week 06	Cohort	90 min	Open Science I: Project Development	Developing Open Projects: Iterative and agile Project management, Open -Source, Software, Hardware, Data
Week 07	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	
	Mentors	60 min	Mentor training	
	Coworking	60 min	Coworking session	
Week 08	Cohort	90 min	Open Science II: Knowledge Dissemination	Sharing Open Project: Preprint publications, DOI and citation, Open protocols, Open Education & Training
Week 09	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	
	Coworking	60 min	Coworking session	
Week 10	Cohort	90 min	Open Science III: Next steps	FAIRification of existing or mature projects
Week 11	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	
	Coworking	60 min	Coworking session	
	Mentors	60 min	Mentor training	
Week 12	Cohort	90 min	Mental health care, Ally skills and Career Guidance Call	
Week 13	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	
	Cohort	90 min	Social Call & Open Agenda	
Week 14	Cohort	90 min	Designing & Empowering for inclusivity	Personas and pathways for contributors, Implicit bias & mental health care, Community interactions & Ally-skill
Week 15	Mentor-Mentee	30 min	Meet your mentor!	Preparation for the final demos
	Cohort	90 min	Final presentation	Test of the final demos

			rehearsal	
Week 16	Cohort	90 min	Final presentations & Graduation!	5-minute demos of projects (Audience: entire community & public, Open and recorded call)
	Mentors	60 min	Mentor wrap up	

Location/Venue (or platform if e-learning):

Online; combination of Zoom for the calls, HackMD for the notes, YouTube for the recording, and GitHub for reporting.

Proposed training dates:

September-December 2020

How will the course materials be made available openly after the course?

Notes, slides, and other materials from all sessions will be stored on a dedicated GitHub repository and linked to from each week's syllabus page (e.g. <https://openlifesci.org/ols-1/week02/>). Recordings of the calls are generally online within 1-2 days at <https://www.youtube.com/c/OpenLifeSci>.

Are you charging a registration fee?

- No